

**LITERATURE REVIEW OF SHOTHAHARA KALPA MENTIONED IN
THE SHARANGDHAR SAMHITA*****¹Vd. Vinita Yadav, ²Vd. Gayatri Gaonkar**

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ABSTRACT

Shotha refers to the localized or any generalized swelling caused by the vitiation of doshas and the obstruction of the strotas. It is characterized by utsedh (swelling), Gaurava (heaviness), shool (Pain), Ushma (Burning), Vivarnata (Discolouration) and changes in the tissue function. The concept of Shotha can be correlated with the term Inflammation according to allopathic science. Both concepts overlap significantly in terms of etiology, pathogenesis, clinical features and treatment goals; although ayurveda presents a more systemic understanding. In Ayurvedic literature there are many formulations mentioned with shothahara properties. In this article we are studying various shothahara kalpas from sharangdhar Samhita an old classical ayurvedic text. The purpose of this study is to make a compilation of all shothahara

kalpas and analyze their mode of action based on its ingredients, bhavana Dravya, Anupan and sevan vidhi. Now a days NSAID's are popularly used to treat inflammations in the body but long term use of these drugs come with some side effects like GI Bleeding, Hypertension, Hepatotoxicity and Renal damage etc. Compared to an allopathic drugs, ayurvedic medicines can be used for a longer duration with lesser or no side effects. Thus it is innovative to list down the medications under shothahara properties and interpret its probable mode of action.

KEYWORDS: Shotha, Chikitsa, Haridra, Sharangdhar Samhita, Shodhan.

INTRODUCTION

Sharangdhara Samhita is a classical text book included in Laghutrayee. It stands as a best example of Ayurvedic Literature of ancient India. The author of this text has followed mainly Charak Samhita, Sushrut Samhita and some other Rasashashtra Granthas. Since the drug manufacturing part is elaborately dealt in this, many physicians now a days prefer the formulations described in this text.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This research is completely literary. Classical text of Rasa shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana is studied and all the shothahara formulations mentioned in it are categorized. The repetitive ingredients are studied in detail to draw a conclusion regarding common properties of shothahara Dravya's.

Concept Of Shotha

[1] Definition

पित्तक्तकफान्वायुरुष्टौ रुष्टान् बहिः पिराः । नीत्वा रुद्धगपिस्तैपि कुयात्त्वत्तिं तिंश्रयम् ॥
उत्सेधि तिंतिं शोफि तिमाहुपनुचयार्तिः ।^[1]

According to Acharya Vagbhat when Pitta, Rakta, Kapha and Vata become vitiated (Dushta) they get carried through bahya sira (superficial blood vessels) and move outward from the deeper tissues to the surface of the body. Then channels (strotas) get obstructed and leads to the accumulation of dosha + dushya in the local area. Because of this accumulation utsedh (raised area), samhat (Hard/firm) swelling (Shotha) is produced.

The classical texts especially Charak Samhita and Sushrut Samhita, dedicate entire chapters to the condition known as Shotha, which represents both oedema (swelling due to fluid accumulation) and edematous inflammation (inflammatory swelling).

INFLAMMATION

Inflammation is seen as the body's natural healing response, characterized by 4 main signs- Rubor (Redness), Calor (Increased heat), Tumor (Swelling) and Dolor (Pain).

[2] Classification of shotha according to Charak Samhita^[2]

(a) Depending upon the site of shotha

1. Ekang Shotha (Localised swelling)

2. Ardhang Shotha (Regional swelling)
3. Sarvang Shotha (Generalised swelling or dropsy)

(b) Depending upon the cause of shotha

1. Nija (Vataj, Pittaj, Kaphaj) 2. Aagantuj.

Table No. 01: Characteristics of Nija Shotha.^[3]

Vataj Shotha	Pittaj Shotha	Kaphaj Shotha
Spreads rapidly	Edema is soft	
Unstable	Reddish and yellow in colour	Edema is heavy stable
Soft	Unpleasant odor	Loss appetite
Skin over edema is dry	Red eye, vertigo, sweating and burning	Salivation
Blackish	Fever	Sleep
Pain and numbness	Tenderness	Non pitting edema
Pitting edema		increases in night
Increases during day and reduced in night	Pus formation	

Table No. 02: Characteristics of Agantuj Shotha.^[4]

Types of Agantuj shotha ^[7]	Causative Factor	Description
Abhighata	Trauma	Injury due to physical impact
Krimi	Infection	Caused by pathogenic organism
Visha	Toxicity	Exposure to poisonous agent
Dahana	Burn	Fire, Hot substances and corrosives
Sagarvata/Himavata	Climatic Changes	Extreme seasonal or weather related influences

Treatment of Shotha^[5]

अथामजिं लङ्गनिचनक्रमै प िंशोधनेरुल्बणर्ोषमापर्िंिः । पशरोगिं शीषुप रेचनैरधो प रेचनैरुर्धु5रैस्तथोर्धुजम् ॥ १७ ॥ ङिचरेिं स्ने5भ िप रूक्षणैिंः प्रकल्पयेिं स्ने5प पधिं च रूक्षजे । प बद्धप ट्केऽपनलजे पनरूऽणिं घृिंिं िु पित्तापनलजे िपिक्तकम् ॥ १८ ॥ ियश्च मूर्च्ाुरपिर्ाऽपिषुिं प शोधनीये िु िमूत्रपमषि । कफोत्थिंिं क्षारकटूष्णिंिंयुिंिंः िमूत्रिकाि युत्थक्तपभजुयेिं ॥ १९ ॥

Table No. 03: It is estimated considering following points.

Sr. No	Condition/Cause	Treatment
01.	Aama Avastha	Langhan Pachan
02.	Bahudoshavastha	Shodhan
03.	Shirogat Shotha	Shirovirechan
04.	Adha Sharir	Virechan
05.	Urdhwa Sharir	Vaman
06.	Santarpanjanya Hetu	Virukshan
07.	Apatarpanjanya Hetu	Snehan
08.	Vibandha Vit	Niruh
09.	Vata Pittaj	Tiktak Ghruta
10.	Murcha Arati Daha Trushna	Ksheerpan
11.	Kaphaj shotha	Kshar Katu Ushna Dravya siddha Gomutra Takra Aasav

Prognosis^[6]

(a) Sadhyatva (Good Prognosis)

अहीनमांसस्य एकदोषजो नवो बलस्थस्य सुखः साधने । Good prognosis – curability:

Aheena mamsa – if there is no muscle wasting in the patient, Eka Doshaja – if only one Dosha is involved

Nava – oedema of recent origin

Balasthasya – if the patient has good strength then the condition is curable.

(b) Asadhyatva (Bad prognosis)

कृशस्य रोगैरबलस्य यो भवेदुपद्रवैवा वममपूवाकैयुतः ।

स हन्ति ममानुगतोऽथ रामजमान् पररस्रवेद्धीनबलस्य सवागः ॥

The patient of Svayathu succumbs to death because of the following:

If oedema occurs in a person who is emaciated and afflicted by other diseases Vami – If the patient of oedema develops complications, like vomiting, etc Marmanugata – If the oedema has afflicted the vital organs of the body

Rajiman – If stripes appears over the oedematous part

Parisrava – If there is exudation of fluid from this oedematous part

Heenabalasya Sarvanuga – If there is general oedema all over the body (anasarca) in a weak patient.

Table No. 04: Shothahara Kalpa and their composition.^[7]

Sr.No	Formulation	Ingredient	Indication
1.	Punarnavadi Kwath	Punarnava, Abhaya, Nimba, Darvi, Tikta, Patola, Guduchi, Nagar, Gomutra	Pandu, Kasa, Udar, Shwas, Shola, Sarvang Shotha
2.	Punarnavadi Kwath	Punarnava, Amruta, Devdaru, Pathya, Nagar, Guggulu, Gomutra	Shotha, Udar
3.	Phalatrik Kwath	Haritaki, Amalaki, Bibhitaki, Gomutra	Vatakaphaj shoth, Vrushan Shotha
4.	Panchavalkal kwath	Ashwatha, Udumbar, Plaksh, vetas, vata	Vrana shotha, Upadansha
5.	Ajmodadi choorna	Ajmoda, Vidang, Saindhav, Devdaru, chitrak, Pippalimula, Shatapushpa, Pippali, marichaPathya, vruddhadaru, Nagar	Shotha, Aamvata, Grudhrasi, Kati Prushta ruja, Tuni, Pratuni, Vishawachi
6.	Lavanbhaskar choorna	Samudra lavana, Sauvarchal lavan, Bida lavan, Saidhav lavan, Pippali, Pippali mula, Krushna jeeraka, Nagakeshar, Talispatra, amlavetas, Maricha, Jeeraka	Arsha, Grahani, Kushta, Shopha, Shwas, Kasa, Aamvat, Mandagni
7.	Navayas Choorna	Haritaki, Amalaki, Bibhitaki, Shunthi, Maricha, Pippali, Vidang, Musta, Chitrak	Pandu, Hrudrog, Bhagandar, Shotha, Kushta, Arsha
8.	Suran Vatak	Suran, Vruddhadaru, Musali, Chitrak, Bibhitaki, Dhatri, Vidanga, Bhallatak, Pippalimula, Talish	Shwas, Kasa, Shotha, Hikka, meha, Bhagandar, Pleeha
9.	Mandur Vatak	Triphala, Trikatu, Chavya, Pippalimula, chitrak, Makshik, Musta, Vidanga, Darvi	Kamala, Pandu, Meha, Arsha, Kushta, Shotha
10.	Yograj Guggulu	Pippali, Pippali mula, Chavya, Chitrak, Nagar, Patha, Vidanga, Katuka, bharangi, ativisha, Vacha, Guggulu	Retodoshhar, Kushtha, Arsha, Grahani, shotha, shola, Udar
11.	Kaishor Guggulu	Triphala, Guduchi, Trikatu, Vidang, Danti, Manjishtha	Prameha, Mandagni, Kasa, Shotha, Pandu
12.	Triphala Guggulu	Triphala, Pippali, Guggulu	Bhagandar, Gulma, shotha, Arsha
13.	Kasisadi Ghruta	Kasis, Haridra, Daruharidra, hartal, manashila, kampilaka, gandhak, vidanga, Guggulu, Marich, Kushta, Tuttha, Manjishtha, Jatamansi, Shirish	Shotha, Bhagandar, Kushta, Dadru, Visarpa, Visphota
14.	Ushirasava	Ushira, Vala, Padmak, Priyangu, Lodhra, Manjishtha, Patha, Kirattikta, Kanchnar, Parpatak, Shalmali niryas	Raktapitta, Pandu, Kushta, Prameha, Krumi, Shotha
15.	Lohasava	Loha, Triphala, Trikatu, Yavani, Vidanga, Musta, Chitrak, Dhataki pushpa,	Pandu, Shotha, Gulma, Udar, Arsha, Kushta, Pleeha, Grahani, Arochak
16.	Rohitakarishtha	Rohitak, Panchakola, Trijata, Triphala	Grahani, Pandu, Hrudroga, Pleeha, Gulma, Shopha
17.	Dashang Lepa	Shirisha, Yashtimadhu, Tagar, Raktachandan, Ela, Jatmansi, Haridra, Daruharidra, Kushta, Vala	Visarpa, Visha, Visphota, shotha, Dushta vrana
18.	Bhallatak Lepa	Ajadugdha, Navneeta, Krushna murtika	Shotha
19.	Vataj	Bijjora nimbu, Hinsra, Devdaru, shunthi,	Vataj Shotha

	shodhahar lepa	Rasna, Agnimantha	
20.	Pittaj Shothahar Lepa	Madhuk, Chandan, Murva, Padmak, Ushir, vala, padmak	Pittaj Shotha
21.	Kapahaj Shothahar Lepa	Krushna, Shigru twak, sikta, Haritaki	Kaphaj Shotha
22.	Raktaj shothahar lepa	Hridra, Daruharidra, Chandan, Raktchandan, Haritaki, Durva, Punarnava, Ushir, Padmak, Lodhra, Gairik, Rasanjan	Raktaj Shotha

Table No. 05: Properties of the repetitive ingredients.^[8]

Sr. No	Dravya Name	Rasa	Veerya	Vipaka	Guna	Rogagnata
1.	Rakta punarnava	Tikta	Sheeta	Katu	Laghu, Vatal, Grahi, Kaphapittahara	Shotha, Raktapitta,
2.	Haridra	Katu Tikta	Ushna	-	Ruksha Varnya, Kaphapittahara	Twak vikar, Meha, Shotha, Pandu Vrananash
3.	Guduchi	Katu Tikta Kashay	Ushna	Madhur	Sangrahini, Laghu, Balya, Agnidipan, Tridoshaghna	Trushna, Daha, Prameha, Kasa, Pandu, Kamala, Kushta, Hrudrog
4.	Haritaki	Madhur Amla katu Tikta kashay	Ushna	Madhur	Rasayan, Laghu, Chakshushya, Bruhana, Anuloman	Shwa, Kasa, Prameh, Arsha, Shotha, Kamala, Ashmari, Mutrakrucha
5.	Amalaki	Madhur Amla Katu Tikta Kashay	Sheeta	Madhur	Vrushya, Rasayan	Raktapitta, Prameh, Amlapitta
6.	Bibhitaki	Kashay	Ushna	Madhur	Bhedan, Ruksha, Keshya, Laghu	Kasa, Krumi, Vaiswarya
7.	Shunthi	Katu	Ushna	Madhur	Laghu, Pachana, Snigdha, Vrushya	Sheepad, Shotha, arsha, Shwas, Hrudrog, Anaha
8.	Marich	Katu	Ushna	Madhur	Tikshna, Deepana, Ruksha, Kaphavatahara	Shwas, Shool, Krumi
9.	Pippali	Katu	Anushana	Madhur	Laghu, Rasayan, Vatakaohara, Rechana	Shwas, Kasa, Uadar, Kushta, Prameha, Gulma, Arsha
10.	Shirish	Madhur Tikta Kashay	Anushna	-	Laghu	Shotha, Visarpa, Kasa, Vrana, Visha
11.	Yashti madhu	Madhur	Sheeta	Madhur	Guru, Snigdha, Chakshuya, Bala, Vadna,	Vrana, Visha, Chardi, Shotha, Trushna Glani

DISCUSSION

Shotha Roga is caused by the vitiation of the tridosha. Under this disease, all the tridoshas of the body get vitiated but according to its Dohsa bheda, a particular dosha is vitiated.

According to the dosha dominance, the treatment protocol is followed. Both Oral Medicines and Local application is beneficial.

Shothahar Yogas contain various ingredients that contain properties which are useful in pacifying the aggravated doshas and clearing the strotas.

CONCLUSION

From the above study, we can conclude that dravyas used in the shothaharad kalpa are usually Ushna, Tikshan, Deepana and Pachana, which causes digestion of the ama, which is the major cause of the shotha. Some of them are mutral dravyas which increase the urine output and thus reducing water retention, used especially in the kapha or meda related shotha. These dravyas also possess vednasathapan (Analgesic Property) and Raktaprasadhan (Blood purification) property which reduces the heat and burning sensation present in the swelling and thus improve the microcirculation.

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